

Identification

Literature Identified by advanced searching in Scopus database using= TITLE-ABS-KEY ("Design") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY ("Creativity") (n= 5,980,330)

Screening

Inclusion Criteria applied and selected only ""brain based learning" (n =186)

Excluded literature (n=5,980,144)

Eligibility

Literature assessed for eligibility (n = 186)

Included

Highly relevant literature included for bibliometric analysis) (n =186)

